

The mediating effect of job stress in the relationship between work-related dimensions and career commitment

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Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to examine associations between career commitment, job stress, and work-related dimensions of work routinization, role clarity, social support, and promotional opportunity.

Design/methodology/approach – 408 employees holding supervisor or above level job positions in Sri Lanka responded to the survey. For the data analysis, structural equation modelling with maximum likelihood estimation was performed.

Findings – Job stress fully mediates the relationship between role clarity and career commitment while partially mediates the relationships between work routinization, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity and career commitment.

Originality/value – An investigation into relationships between work-related dimensions and career commitment holds a number of implications in the current business environment where employee commitment may be shifting from the organization to one's career.

Keywords career commitment, job stress, promotional opportunity, role clarity, work routinization.

Paper type Research paper

Introduction

Job stress, which has been recognised as an important occupational health problem, may be encountered in every key element in a particular job (Cooper, 2005). The literature provides evidence that work-related dimensions such as work routinization, the lack of role clarity, the quality of social environment in the workplace, and unclear promotion prospects have generated unprecedented levels of job stress in organisations (Cooper, 2005; Schabracq and Cooper, 2000; Noblet and Rodwell, 2008; Yang *et al.*, 2008). The literature also provides evidence that one of the negative consequences of prolonged exposure to job stress is the lack of career commitment (Van der Heijden *et al.*, 2009).

Therefore, it is important to analyse the relationship between work-related dimensions, job stress and career commitment in an extended framework by taking into account how work-related antecedents affect job stress and how job stress in turn impacts on employees' commitment to their career. Such an investigation could provide valuable information for academics and practitioners alike as, first, the workplace stands out as a potentially important source of stress because of the amount of time that is spent in this setting (Erkutlu and Chafra, 2006). Second, previous studies reveal that career commitment of white-collar employees is important as their level of career commitment may influence their love for the profession, which is related to several other variables such as career stage, career pattern and satisfaction with career progression (Myrtle *et al.*, 2008; Popoola and Oluwole, 2007). Although many predictors of job stress have been found by the previous researchers (e.g., Johnson *et al.*, 2005; Yang *et al.*, 2008), there needs to be more work undertaken to understand the influence of work environment on job stress and in turn on career commitment.

Building on previous research, the specific aim of this study was to examine the relationship between work-related dimensions (i.e., work routinization, role clarity, social

support, and promotional opportunity), job stress and career commitment of employees holding supervisor or above level job positions. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information to better understand suitable practices to be adopted in organizations. Further, it is expected that the findings of this study will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Job stress and sources of job stress

Job stress is generally defined in the literature as an employee's feeling of job-related hardness, tension, anxiety, frustration, worry, emotional exhaustion and distress (Armstrong and Griffin, 2004). In other words, work-related variables (job stressors), when interpreted by the individual (cognitive interpretation), may lead to stress (Dua, 1994). Therefore, stressors denote the external force or situation acting on the individual - objective events. Stress denotes the deformation or changes produced in the individual as a result of those forces - subjective experience of the event (Le Fevre *et al.*, 2003).

A number of aspects of working life have been identified as linked to stress (Van der Heijden *et al.*, 2009; Yang *et al.*, 2008). For instance, organizational practices such as redundancy and unclear promotion prospects (e.g. Erkutlu and Chafra, 2006; Yang *et al.*, 2008), task features such as role clarity (e.g. Nelson and Burke, 2000; Siegall, 2000), work routinization (e.g. Gold *et al.*, 2006; Price, 1997), and the quality of social support (e.g. Price, 1997) have been frequently identified as work-related dimensions that may affect job stress (positively or negatively). In the above context, this study investigated whether job stress mediates between four work-related dimensions (i.e., work routinization, role clarity, social support, and promotional opportunity) and career commitment.

Work routinization. This is the degree to which a job is repetitive (Price, 1997). A high degree of repetitiveness signifies a highly routinized job (Price, 1997). Scholars identify work routinization under a diversity of labels, such as task variety, task variability, formatted tasks, task predictability, and work-flow predictability (see Gold *et al.*, 2006; Price, 1997). The literature suggests two extreme ends in the continuum of the level of work “routineness”. The one end is where work is performed regularly and contains no or few variable work elements, so that the frequency of occurrence, total work cycle (duration) and content (sequence of elements) vary little or not at all. The other end is where there is no easily defined work cycle at all and the employee’s activity cannot readily be predicted for any given point in time or there is very high variability in the work element frequency, duration or content (Gold *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 1. Work routinization will be significantly positively related to job stress.

Role clarity. This is the degree to which an individual perceives that the required information is provided on how he or she is expected to perform his or her job (Teas *et al.*, 1979). The literature identifies the lack of clarity about the role expectations as role ambiguity (see Price, 1997) whereas Rizzo *et al.* (1970) identify role ambiguity to be related to an individual who lacks clear direction on the expectations of his or her role in the job or organization. Hence, role ambiguity arises when individuals do not have a clear picture of their work objectives, co-workers’ expectation of them, and scope and responsibilities of the job. Several previous research identified the lack of clarity about the job as an important antecedents to job stress (e.g., Nelson and Burke, 2000; Siegall, 2000; Van der Heijden *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 2. Role clarity will be significantly negatively related to job stress.

Social support. This refers to helping relationships that come from co-workers, immediate supervisor, the friends outside of work, and partners (or spouse) regarding work-related matters (Price, 1997). In the current study, the term social support is confined to helping relationships that come from co-workers and the immediate supervisor. Several previous research have investigated social support in the context of the current study (e.g., Burke, 1988; Noblet and Rodwell, 2008; Yang *et al.*, 2008). For instance, Yang *et al.* (2008) provided evidence that high-quality relationships make it possible for employees to gain more social support and social resources from supervisors and co-workers to accomplish tasks and cope with negative emotions. The lack of helping relationships that come from co-workers and the immediate supervisor had therefore been identified as a source of job stress, and the lack of employees' well-being at work (e.g. Burke, 1988; Noblet and Rodwell, 2008; Yang *et al.*, 2008). The literature suggests that strain felt by employees increases when demands of the job situation are not matched by adequate levels of support from supervisors and colleagues (Noblet and Rodwell, 2008; Yang *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 3: The existence of social support will be significantly negatively related to job stress.

Promotional opportunity. The lack of opportunities for advancement, which individuals being dependent upon their performance, makes the work situation potentially very stressful (see Erkutlu and Chafra, 2006). The existence of a series of job ladders and the existence of internal labour market, where to a greater extent vacancies are filled from within the organization, can be identified as providing avenues for movement between different status levels within an organization (see Price, 1997). The lack of promotional opportunity has been identified as an important antecedent to job stress (e.g., Nelson and Burke, 2000; Yang *et al.*, 2008). For instance, Yang *et al.* (2008) found that employees with a higher level of

opportunities for advancement demonstrate a higher level of psychological and physical well-being. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 4: The lack of promotional opportunity will be significantly positively related to job stress.

Career commitment

Career commitment is referred to identification with and involvement in one's occupation, which signifies the degree of loyalty to one's profession (e.g. Mueller *et al.*, 1999). The literature also identifies career commitment as the strength of one's motivation to work in a chosen career role (Hall, 1971) as well as the degree of loyalty to one's profession (e.g. Blau, 1985; Mueller *et al.*, 1999). The literature suggests that commitment to one's career seems to develop gradually and change over the course of one's career (Noordin *et al.*, 2002). This is important since the literature provides evidence for a shift from organizationally-based careers to individually-owned careers, which are beyond the boundary of any one organization (Arthur and Rousseau, 1996; McDonald *et al.*, 2005; Hall, 2004). In this regard, Arthur *et al.* (2005) argued that borderless or protean careers are independent of organizational boundaries and careers are increasingly under the control of individuals. Yet, the literature identifies careers as products of organizational life (Ballout, 2009; Kidd and Green, 2006) and asserts the importance of involvement of not only employees but also employing organizations in career management (Ballout, 2009; Snape and Redman, 2003).

Job stress and career commitment. Previous research has paid less attention to the impact of job stress as a possible cause for the lack of career commitment. Although it is very difficult to find direct empirical research on the impact of job stress on career commitment, previous research has shown that dissatisfaction with the characteristics of work environment

(including routinization and supervisory relations) may affect employees' intention to leave their profession (e.g. Blau, 2007; Blau and Lunz, 1998; Van der Heijden *et al.*, 2009). Further, Lee *et al.* (2000) examined the relationship between career commitment and person and work-related variables meta-analytically and concluded that attitudes toward the job itself may be a central concern in committing to one's occupation. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 5. Job stress will be significantly negatively related to career commitment.

The mediating effect of job stress in the relationship between work-related dimensions and career commitment. Previous research provides evidence that work intensification, role ambiguity and role conflict lead to a higher level of job stress which in turn lower job satisfaction (Zeytinoglu *et al.*, 2007). The current study proposed that employees who will report more stress from work routinization and the lack of promotional opportunity will report a lower level of career commitment (refer to Figure 1). In a similar vein, employees who will report a lower level of stress from role clarity and the existence of helping relationships with others (co-workers and the immediate supervisor) will report a higher level of career commitment. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 6. Job stress will mediate the relationship between work-related dimensions of (a) work routinization, (b) role clarity, (c) relationships with others, and (d) the lack of promotional opportunity and career commitment.

In testing the mediator effect, direct relationships between work-related variables and career commitment have to be hypothesised. In this regard, past research identifies direct

relationships between work-related variables and career commitment (e.g. Adio and Popoola, 2010; Kidd and Smewing, 2001; Popoola and Oluwole, 2007; Van der Heijden *et al.*, 2009). Specifically, previous research (Kidd and Smewing, 2001; Van der Heijden *et al.*, 2009) provided evidence that non-supportive work environment and the lack of work relations negatively influence employees' career commitment. Further, previous research provided evidence that the lack of role clarity (Aryee and Tan, 1992) and perceived rewards including promotional opportunity (Adio and Popoola, 2010; Popoola and Oluwole, 2007) negatively influence employees' career commitment. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 7. (a) Work routinization and (b) the lack of promotional opportunity will be significantly negatively related to career commitment while (c) role clarity and (d) the existence of helping relationships with others will be significantly positively related to career commitment.

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed relationships.

Take in Figure I

Method

Measures

Career commitment was measured by the three items from Mueller *et al.* (1999) on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). An example item includes "I speak highly of my profession to my friends". The higher number indicates a higher level of career commitment. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach's alpha=.892, eigenvalue=3.50, and explained variation=70.15%.

Job stress was measured using the five items from Lambert *et al.* (2006) on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). An example item includes “I am usually under a lot of pressure when I am at work”. The higher number indicates a higher level of job stress. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.889, eigenvalue=4.22, and explained variation=60.24%.

Work routinization, the degree to which the job is repetitive, was measured by the five items adapted from Price (1997) on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The adapted items are “My job requires me to do same things over and over again”, “My job requires a high level of skill (reverse)”, “My job requires me to do a number of different things (reverse)”, “No creativity is required in my job”, and “My job requires me to keep learning new things (reverse)”. The higher number indicates a higher level of work routinization. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.802, eigenvalue=1.67, and explained variation=83.44%.

Role clarity was measured using the six items from Rizzo *et al.* (1970) on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Example items include “I know exactly what is expected of me in my job“, and “I know what my responsibilities are”. The higher number indicates a higher level of role clarity. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach’s alpha=.870, eigenvalue=1.77, and explained variation=88.49%.

Social support was measured using the six items from Price (1997) on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Example items include “My immediate supervisor is willing to listen to my job-related problems”, “My immediate supervisor shows a lot of concern for me on my job”, and “I am very friendly with one or more of my co-workers”. The higher number indicates a higher level of helping

relationships. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach's alpha=.907, eigenvalue=3.13, and explained variation=78.31%.

The lack of promotional opportunity, i.e., the lack of movement between different status levels within an organization, was measured using the six items from Iverson and Roy (1994) on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Example items include "Promotions are infrequent" and "Promotions are very rare". The higher number indicates a lower level of promotional opportunity. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardized Cronbach's alpha=.755, eigenvalue=2.02, and explained variation=67.32%.

The demographic variables measured in the study were gender (female=0, male=1), marital status (single=0, married=1), age (continuous scale), the highest level of education (without a degree =0, with a degree=1), and the years of experience in the present workplace (continuous scale).

Sample and method of data collection

The target population for the study is a broad cross-section of employees holding supervisor or above level job positions and engaged full time in private sector firms located in Colombo, which is considered as the main commercial and financial hub of Sri Lanka. The three available directories, i.e., Colombo Stock Exchange, the Registrar of Companies, and business section of the Sri Lanka Telecom Telephone Directory were used to identify possible medium to large scale firms belong to different industries having 150 or more employees. With the help of the directories, a random sample of 180 organizations was selected.

For the study, survey method was used and the questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of people that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to

distribution. Contact persons were identified through commercial and financial associations, employees' welfare associations or trade unions, educational programmes offered for the intended categories of employees by educational institutes, and personal networks to distribute the final version of the self-administered survey questionnaire. The contact persons distributed the survey questionnaire among a heterogeneous sample of employees ranked at different levels within the organizations. Participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution, and their responses were anonymous. Of the 600 self-administered questionnaires sent out, 408 completed questionnaires yielded a response rate of 68%.

The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table I. As can be seen from Table I, 71% were males while 29% were females. 58% married while 42% reported single. 35% were less than 35 years of age, 57% belonged to the age range of 35 to 50 years of age, while 8% were above 50 years of age. 32% reported total tenure in the present work place as less than 5 years, 44% reported to have 5 to 10 years of tenure while 24% reported to have more than 10 years of tenure in the present work place. 63% had Bachelor's or postgraduate degree as the highest level of education.

Take in Table I

Methods of data analysis

Harman's single-factor test was conducted; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff *et al.* (2003). For all measurement scales, Cronbach's alpha was examined and Principal components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than

1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair *et al.*, 2006). Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), correlation analysis and path analysis were used to meet the objectives of the study. For the path analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS 16.

Results and discussion

Table II shows means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations among the variables. When considering correlations between four independent variables (in Table II), the correlation between role clarity and social support is comparatively high (.446) compared to all the other combinations of correlations between four independent variables. Yet, variance inflation factor (VIF) that ranged from 1.17 to 1.25 suggested collinearity is not an issue in the data (see Hair *et al.*, 2006).

Take in Table II

Structural path coefficients were estimated using Amos 16. Figure II shows the research model with standardised path loadings. The summary of results is provided in Table III. Fit measures relating to absolute fit (CMIN/df, GFI), relative fit (CFI), parsimonious fit (PRATIO), and fit measures based on the non-central chi-square distribution (RMSEA, PCLOSE) were used to evaluate the model-data fit (see Hair *et al.*, 2006). The structural model had CMIN/df=13.96, GFI=0.89, CFI=0.88, PRATIO=0.80, RMSEA=0.04, and PCLOSE=0.72. The model well satisfied the requirements of goodness-of-fit criteria (see Hair *et al.*, 2006).

As can be seen in Table III, all the direct relationships hypothesised for the study (i.e., H1 to H5) were supported by the data. Further, H7(a), (c), and (d) were supported, and as a consequence H6(a), (c), and (d) were supported suggesting partial mediation. However, H7(b) was not supported, and as a consequence H6(d) was supported suggesting full mediation.

When discussing the results in detail, squared multiple correlation of .216 suggests that work routinization, role clarity, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity account for 22% of the variation of job stress. Squared multiple correlation of .399 suggests that job stress, work routinization, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity account for 40% of the variation of career commitment. In addition to the statistical evidence for direct relationships between work routinization, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity and career commitment, there are indirect effects between work routinization, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity and career commitment through job stress. Hence, job stress partially mediates the relationships between work routinization, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity and career commitment. Since the direct relationship between role clarity and career commitment is not significant, the study provides statistical evidence for full-mediation of job stress in the relationship between role clarity and career commitment.

Take in Table III

Take in Figure II

Conclusions and implications

The article presented findings of a study that investigated the relationship between four work-related dimensions, job stress and career commitment. Whilst it is recognised that

today's workplace environment stands out as an important source of stress and employee commitment may be shifting from the organization to one's career, it is very rare to find studies that investigated the effect of job stress in the relationship between work-related dimensions and career commitment. The study tested a job specific model of stress depicting general relationships of sources and consequences of job stress rather than examining relationships existing in specific or unique job contexts.

As anticipated, it was found that the four work-related dimensions, i.e., work routinization, role clarity, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity have significant direct effect on job stress. For instance, when a job contains a higher degree of repetitiveness with few variable work elements, individuals may experience a higher level of job stress; when clarity about the job is lacking, they may experience a higher level of job stress; when employees do not receive social support from co-workers and supervisor to accomplish tasks, they may experience a higher level of job stress; and when individuals are not provided with avenues for promotion, they may experience a higher level of job stress. These findings support previous studies that found job stress is affected by work routinization (e.g. Gold *et al.*, 2006; Price, 1997), role clarity (e.g. Nelson and Burke, 2000; Siegall, 2000), relationships with others (e.g. Noblet and Rodwell, 2008; Yang *et al.*, 2008), and promotional opportunity (e.g. Nelson and Burke, 2000; Yang *et al.*, 2008).

Further, work routinization, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity have significant direct effect on career commitment. For instance, when a job contains a higher degree of variety, individuals may experience a higher level of career commitment; when employees receive social support in the work context, they may experience a higher level of career commitment; and when individuals are provided with avenues for advancement, they may experience a higher level of career commitment. Previous studies such as Popoola and Oluwole (2007), Kidd and Smewing (2001) and Van der Heijden *et al.*

(2009) also provided evidence to these direct relationships. However, the findings of the current study do not support the findings of Aryee and Tan (1992), where they found a significant relationship between role clarity and career commitment. This non-significant relationship between role clarity and career commitment may imply that under the current business environment with short-term contract culture of employment, job uncertainties due to corporate restructuring, and changes in organisational strategies providing individuals with specific details about the job is difficult, and individuals may also consider this as a normal event. Hence, the lack of clarity does not impact on individuals' career commitment.

As anticipated, the current study found a significant direct relationship between job stress and career commitment. Further, as anticipated, the study found that job stress mediates the relationships between all the four work-related dimensions and career commitment. Specifically, job stress fully mediates the relationship between role clarity and career commitment while partially mediates the relationships between work routinization, social support, and the lack of promotional opportunity and career commitment. Therefore, the findings of the current study suggest that the characteristics of work environment (namely, routinization, role clarity, social support, and promotional opportunity) create job stress in individuals, which in turn negatively impact on their career commitment. However, more empirical work is needed to test the propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm these findings.

Overall, the findings presented in this paper would be valuable for academics and practitioners alike. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, the findings of the study contribute to the literature by examining work-related dimensions, job stress and career commitment in an extended framework. However, it is very rare to find previous empirical studies that investigated the links proposed in this study to make straight forward

comparisons. Therefore, the findings of this study would provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the practice, practitioners need valid information to guide their actions in enhancing favourable work-related attitudes and behaviour. First, the findings could be used to generate new ideas for designing and redesigning jobs to make them more productive, more fulfilling, and more learning-inducing to the holder. For instance, an understanding of links between job stress, career commitment, work routinization, role clarity, and promotional opportunity will help designing jobs which can stimulate learning, growth, and employability on the part of the job holder. Hence, such findings are important for organizations in designing and redesigning smart jobs. Second, the findings of the study imply the importance of co-workers and supervisors having capabilities to support employees in their chosen career role by providing support for newcomers in adjusting to the organization and creating a supportive organizational climate.

Third, according to today's career contract individuals are ultimately responsible for pursuing and managing their own careers (Arthur and Rousseau, 1996). For instance, awareness and identification of specific work-related sources of job stress that could influence career commitment may help individuals to anticipate and manage career-detachment behaviours. Fourth, having an understanding of work-related dimensions that lead to job stress, which in turn influence career commitment would help individuals to develop a set of personal skills and competencies such as continuous learning and tolerance for ambiguity and uncertainty to maintain membership in his or her chosen career.

Limitations and future research

This study was designed as a cross-sectional study employing quantitative methodology. Although one can envisage a wide range of sources of stress within the work environment,

the current study was confined to investigate four work-related dimensions. Further, the study was designed to investigate the mediating effect of work environment factors on job stress and in turn on career commitment. Building on the previous research, the current study took into account direct relationships between work dimensions and job stress. However, some variables, such as promotional opportunity could also be analyzed as moderators coupling with appropriate independent variables. Future research could incorporate such variables. Finally, current study was not confined to a particular industry. Therefore, one could argue that a particular workplace factor may not consistently relate to stress in all workplaces. Hence, future research could confine their samples to a particular industry or profession. Further, future studies could explore white collar employees' stress coping styles as well as interventions introduced by organisations to reduce job stress.

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Figures

Figure I: Hypothesised research model (simplified)

Figure II. Structural path estimates

Note: Standardized estimates are reported.

Tables

Table I: Characteristics of the sample

<i>Specialised area of work:</i>		<i>Age:</i>	
Technical (e.g. engineering, IT, production, and scientific in nature)	37%	Less than 35 years	35%
		35-50 years	57%
Accounting and financial	22%	Over 50 years	8%
Marketing	21%		
General Administration	20%	<i>Work experience:</i>	
		Less than 5 years	32%
		5-10	44%
<i>Gender:</i>		Over 10 years	24%
Male	71%		
Female	29%		
		<i>Highest level of education:</i>	
<i>Marital status:</i>		With out a degree	37%
Married	58%	With a degree (Bachelor's or postgraduate degree)	63%
Single	42%		

Table II: Correlations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Age	1									
2. Gender ^a	.033**	1								
3. Marital status ^a	.146*	-.021	1							
4. Tenure	.360**	.093	.299**	1						
5. Education ^a	.017	.026	-.028	.066	1					
6. Work routinization	.086	.025	-.038	-.038	-.052	1				
7. Role clarity	-.123*	.092	.055	.031	.078	.071	1			
8. Social support	-.150**	.038	-.023	-.117*	.173*	-.039	.446**	1		
9. Lack of promotional opportunity	.082	.070	-.082	.009	-.240**	.370**	.130**	.126*	1	
10. Job stress	.203**	-.063	-.074	.101*	-.283**	.196**	-.323**	-.361**	.113*	1
11. Career commitment	-.207**	-.095	.036	-.084	.217**	-.294**	.113*	.364**	-.242**	-.557**

Note. ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables.

Table III: Summary of the results - structural model coefficients

Path	Result	Standardized regression estimate: Direct effect	Standardized regression estimate: Indirect effect	Squared multiple correlation
Work routinization → Job stress	Supported H1	.183**	-	
Role clarity → Job stress	Supported H2	-.283***	-	
Social support → Job stress	Supported H3	-.314***	-	.216
Lack of promotional opportunity → Job stress	Supported H4	.124*	-	
Job stress → Career commitment	Supported H5	-.442***	-	
Work routinization → Career commitment	Supported H7(a) and H6(a), partial mediation	-.170**	-.081	
Role clarity → Career commitment	Not Supported H7(b), Supported H6(b), full mediation	.006	.125	.399
Social support → Career commitment	Supported H7(c) and H6(c), partial mediation	.262***	.139	
Lack of promotional opportunity → Career commitment	Supported H7(d) and H6(d), partial mediation	-.175***	-.055	

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$